

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS WITH AI TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' PRACTICAL SKILLS

Baisova G.

master's degree, Webster University in Tashkent

ABSTRACT

This article examines the integration of virtual learning environments (VLE) with artificial intelligence (AI) to improve students' practical skills. It provides an overview of existing methods such as machine learning (ML), simulation, virtual reality technologies, chatbots, and virtual assistants. Special attention is given to the interaction between students and AI in the educational process. The results of a study analyzing the impact of AI on students' academic performance, engagement, and autonomy in disciplines requiring practical knowledge, such as medicine, engineering, and economics, are discussed.

Keywords: virtual learning environments (VLE), artificial intelligence (AI), practical skills, education, simulations, personalization, engagement, students.

Introduction

With the rapid development of digital technologies, educational systems around the world are facing the need to modernize teaching processes. Virtual learning environments (VLE) have become an essential element of modern education, allowing students to access learning materials, interact with teachers and peers, and study in a convenient online format. However, to maximize the efficiency of VLE, the integration of innovative solutions, such as artificial intelligence (AI), is required, which can significantly transform approaches to teaching and improving students' practical skills.

In recent years, AI has played an important role in educational technologies. It is used to create intelligent learning systems that can adapt to individual student needs, provide constant feedback, and support the learning process through personalized methods. VLE integrated with AI allow students to actively engage in the learning process, not just acquiring theoretical knowledge, but also mastering important practical skills. This is especially relevant in fields such as engineering, medicine, and economics, where the practical application of knowledge is crucial. The purpose of this paper is to review approaches to AI integration in VLE and their impact on improving students' practical skills.

Main part. Overview of existing methods and technologies for AI integration in VLE

Modern educational technologies actively integrate AI elements into learning environments, including virtual ones, to improve the learning process and enhance students' practical skills. These technologies play an important role in ensuring personalized learning, interactive engagement, and creating conditions for hands-on training. One of the integration methods is **machine learning (ML)**. These systems can analyze large amounts of data collected during the learning process and, based on it, offer individualized educational programs for students [1]. With ML, it is possible to predict student behavior, academic performance, and the need for additional support. For instance, the system can identify topics where a student requires extra help

and offer additional materials or assignments to strengthen specific skills. The use of ML also improves knowledge assessment and real-time monitoring of progress, which is especially important when performing coursework and exams, where the analysis of answers can be automated with high accuracy. Adaptive systems based on ML create dynamic learning paths tailored to the individual needs of each student, significantly increasing learning effectiveness and flexibility, especially in distance and hybrid formats.

The use of **virtual assistants and chatbots** to enhance interactivity has become an integral part of interactive VLE. These technologies, based on natural language processing, allow students to interact with the learning environment by asking questions and receiving instant responses in text or voice format [2]. Chatbots play an important role in providing immediate support to students. They can answer frequently asked questions, clarify complex concepts, and even assist with organizational matters such as class schedules or assignment deadlines [3]. This allows students to quickly resolve issues without waiting for a response from a teacher, which is especially important in large-scale courses with many participants. Intelligent virtual assistants can analyze student behavior and offer personalized recommendations for studying materials and completing practical tasks. In some cases, these assistants can develop study plans tailored to each student's knowledge level, thus maintaining their motivation and engagement in the learning process. The integration of **simulations and virtual reality technologies** into VLE provides students with the opportunity to acquire practical skills in a safe and controlled environment [4]. These technologies are especially useful in disciplines that require the mastery of complex manipulations, where mistakes can have serious consequences.

The integration of AI depends on the discipline, as each area requires a unique approach to learning and developing practical skills. Different methods and AI technologies are used in various fields, adapted to solve specific educational tasks (table 1).

Table 1.

Comparison of AI-based approaches in different disciplines [5, 6]

Method/Technology	Medicine	Engineering	Economics and management
Machine learning	Diagnosis prediction, automatic analysis of patient data	Analysis of experimental data, optimization of engineering solutions	Big data analysis, business decision forecasting
Adaptive systems	Personalized training plans for medical practitioners	Adaptive simulations of engineering processes	Personalized business case study programs
Virtual assistants	Virtual assistants for the practice of medical cases	Chatbots to help you work with engineering software	Chatbots to support students in solving problems
Chatbots	Answers to questions about symptoms and procedures	Answers to technical questions, assistance in setting up models	Support in data analysis and management tasks
Simulations	Medical simulators for practicing procedures	Virtual laboratories for working with mechanisms	Financial simulations for decision-making practice
Virtual reality	Simulation of operations and interaction with patients	Modeling of complex engineering systems	Modeling of market situations and business processes

In the author's opinion, such integration demonstrates high effectiveness across various disciplines, adapting to the specific needs of each field. In medicine, AI allows for the simulation of complex clinical procedures, offering personalized learning plans and providing decision-making support [7]. In engineering, the focus is on simulations and virtual laboratories, enabling students to work with virtual models and optimize technical processes. In economics and management, AI is actively applied for data analysis, business scenario modeling, and decision-making support. Thus, each AI method finds its unique application depending on the discipline, contributing to a deeper and more effective mastery of both theoretical and practical knowledge [8]. These technologies not only improve the quality of education but also allow students to practice practical skills in a controlled and adaptive environment, which is crucial for preparing for professional activities.

The use of AI in VLE

AI-integrated virtual learning platforms are capable of adapting curricula, providing personalized recommendations, and simulating practical tasks in a safe digital environment. These tools help students not only to acquire theoretical knowledge but also to improve practical skills through repetitive interactive exercises. However, to better understand how effectively AI contributes to the development of practical skills among students, a practical study is necessary.

Methods

To validate the hypothesis about the positive impact of AI usage in VLE on students' practical skills, an

empirical study was conducted. The sample consisted of students from three major universities specializing in medical, engineering, and economic disciplines. A total of 300 students participated in the study, divided into three groups of 100 students each, based on their field of study. Each group was divided into experimental and control subgroups, with 50 students in each. The experimental group used VLE with integrated AI, while the control group followed traditional programs without AI. The study was conducted over the course of one academic semester. The following data collection methods were used to analyze the effectiveness of AI in learning:

- Student testing on theoretical knowledge and the ability to apply it in practice at the beginning and end of the semester.
- Student surveys to gather feedback on the quality of learning materials and engagement in the learning process.
- Observation of student progress in performing practical tasks and exams, especially in disciplines requiring the application of skills in simulation environments.

After the academic semester, statistical analysis of the data was conducted to compare the performance and engagement of students in the experimental and control groups.

Results

Students using AI showed significant improvements in performance compared to the control group (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of performance results before and after the experiment

The results show that the experimental groups using AI technologies experienced a significant improvement in performance, especially in practical skills. In the medical discipline, students using AI simulators achieved higher scores (average 4,1) compared to the control group (average 3,0). Engineering and economics disciplines also showed an increase in performance in the experimental groups (4,4 and 4,6, respectively), indicating a positive impact of AI on learning and skill development necessary for practical activities.

In disciplines where practical work plays a significant role (engineering, medicine), students in the experimental group completed more tasks, demonstrating

an 85-90% success rate compared to 70-75% in the control groups. Students using AI made 25% fewer mistakes and completed tasks faster than their peers trained in traditional programs. Thus, the data confirm the hypothesis that the integration of AI into educational processes contributes to the improvement of both theoretical and practical skills, making this approach promising for the further development of educational technologies.

Using AI in VLE not only improves academic performance but also has a positive effect on student engagement in the learning process and their ability to work independently (fig.2).

Figure 2. Results of changes in student engagement levels before and after the experiment

Engagement levels in the experimental groups increased by 10-15% compared to the control groups. This is due to the adaptability of AI, which helps each student work at their own pace, providing personalized assignments and feedback. For example, in medical disciplines, student engagement increased from 54,9% to 65,7% after using AI.

In AI-supported VLE, students demonstrated greater independence. Thanks to chatbots and intelligent assistants, they were able to resolve questions during the learning process without waiting for a response from the instructor. This led to a reduction in task completion time and an increase in self-control. Over 80%

of students noted that using AI contributed to their confidence in completing tasks independently. Continuous feedback from AI and the ability to track their progress in real-time increased student motivation to continue learning. They more frequently initiated additional tasks and actively participated in simulations. Thus, the use of AI in VLE positively affects not only academic performance but also student motivation and engagement in the learning process, which in turn enhances their level of independence and readiness for real-world practice.

Discussion

The results of the study confirmed the hypothesis that the integration of AI into VLE positively impacts

student learning, particularly in terms of practical skills and engagement. Students in the experimental groups who used AI demonstrated higher results compared to the control groups using traditional teaching methods. This improvement was seen in both academic performance and practical skills, emphasizing the importance of AI in educational processes.

One of the main advantages of AI is its ability to adapt learning materials to the individual needs of each student. Using ML, student behavior and performance are analyzed, offering personalized learning paths and materials. This increases the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition, as students work at their own pace and receive assignments tailored to their specific difficulties. Virtual assistants and chatbots integrated into VLE allow students to solve issues independently, fostering autonomy. This is especially important in distance learning, where there is no direct interaction with instructors. Practical simulations with AI enhance the development of practical skills, particularly in medical and engineering disciplines, where students can practice manipulations in a safe VLE. The introduction of AI has automated processes such as job evaluation, providing feedback, and creating personalized tasks. This significantly reduces the workload on instructors, freeing up time for more meaningful interactions with students and improving the quality of teaching.

Conclusion

The integration of VLE with AI opens new opportunities for improving educational processes and developing practical skills in students. The results of the study demonstrated that students using AI-supported VLE achieve better academic performance and exhibit higher engagement levels compared to traditional learning methods.

The implementation of AI allows educational programs to be tailored to the individual needs of students, creating personalized learning paths and providing immediate feedback. Virtual simulations with AI are especially useful in areas that require extensive practice, such as medicine and engineering. These simulations enable students to safely and effectively develop practical skills crucial for their future professional activities. These technologies also promote greater student independence. Intelligent virtual assistants and chatbots help students solve learning tasks in real-time, supporting their motivation and engagement in the learning process. Instructors, in turn, can focus on more complex aspects of teaching, as AI takes over the automation of routine tasks.

Thus, the use of AI proves its high effectiveness and demonstrates its potential for further improving educational processes. The integration of AI not only enhances the quality of education but also makes the process more interactive and flexible, preparing students for successful professional careers.

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